

MGL-Drug Conjugate: A Novel Glycan-Targeted Approach for Targeting Cancer Cells

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Cancer continues to pose a significant global health challenge and remains one of the leading causes of death. Despite notable advancements, many existing treatments still fall short in effectiveness and are often accompanied by difficult side effects. [1]. Antibody-Drug Conjugates (ADCs) are effective therapeutic tools, however, they often target protein receptors that are also found on normal cells, limiting their true cancer-specific delivery. Lectins offer a promising strategy for selectively targeting cancer cells while sparing healthy tissues. The human macrophage galactose-type lectin (MGL), expressed on antigen-presenting cells like dendritic cells and macrophages, stands out for its specific recognition of N-acetylgalactosamine (GalNAc) residues in tumour-associated glycans [2, 3, 4]. MGL has the distinct ability to bind both the Tn-antigen (GalNAc α 1-O-Ser/Thr) and its sialylated derivative, sTn (Neu5Ac α 2-6GalNAc α 1-O-Ser/Thr), which are characteristic of cancer cells and are absent on normal, healthy cells.

In this presentation, we share our latest progress in developing innovative MGL-drug conjugate. We selected MMAE, a FDA-approved antimitotic agent in ADCs [5], and incorporated a cleavable linker to enable controlled release. For precise drug attachment, we engineered an MGL construct with a C-terminal cysteine residue [6]. Conjugation reactions were monitored by mass spectrometry, while NMR spectroscopy and biophysical techniques confirmed that the protein retained its structure, stability and binding ability. Preliminary studies, using glycoengineered cancer cell models, have also allowed us to thoroughly evaluate the binding selectivity and toxicity of the MGL-drug conjugate.

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